

SOCIO-CULTURAL DETERMINANTS OF FEMALE CRIMINALITY IN PUNJAB PROVINCE OF PAKISTAN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16948295>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
26 May, 2025	01 July, 2025	01 August, 2025	26 August, 2025

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to explore the socio-cultural and economic determinants of female criminality in Punjab, Pakistan. A total of (N= 32) convicted women imprisoned in thirteen jails of the Punjab were selected for this study. Semi-structured interview guide was used to collect the data through purposive sampling technique. After organizing the data, key notes were taken; codes, themes and attitude & behavior were explored. The results of the study reflected that females were involved in the serious nature of crimes i.e. murder, attempt murder, drug trafficking, theft, kidnapping and child trafficking. The results further demonstrated that unhealthy environment of family, domestic violence and Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) were found as key determinants of female crime. Besides the above, forced marriages, early age marriages, extramarital affairs of husband and wife, family criminal history, refusal of inheritance property rights, influence of peers and preference to take revenge, poverty, unemployment and lust for money were also explored major factors behind the crime committed by convicted women. The study concluded that overall crime is social evil and spreading speedily day by day. Female are forced to adopt criminal behavior because of socio-cultural factors. The study recommended that it is dire need to recognize female criminality as an important issue which is becoming challenge for the both state and society. The relevant stakeholders i.e. government, non-government organizations & civil society must take corrective measures to minimize female criminality. The corrective measures include education, awareness raising programs, strengthening the criminal justice system, proper execution of laws related to gender base & domestic and inheritance property rights.

Key words: Female criminality, family environment, Intimate Partner Violence (IPV), domestic violence.

INTRODUCTION

Women are particularly admired in Pakistan as a symbol of family cohesion, a guardian of traditions, morals, communal norms, and way of living (Islam, Farooq & Mahmood, 2019). However, women have entered in the workforce labor due to socio-cultural and economic disparity in the country. Pakistan is enlisted in the category of developing countries and lack of interest on the research regarding female criminality is observed. The major reason of lack of interest of the researchers is low participation of women in the field of crime.

Therefore, the issues faced by criminal women are not taken serious in the society (Avais & Wassan, 2017). It is the fact that female criminals are lower as compared to male criminals. However, female crime rate is rising gradually not only in Pakistan but also in all over the world (Gainsborough, 2008; Ferdoos & Hafeez, 2016).

In Pakistan, the question regarding factors behinds the female criminality is still answerable. Subramaniam (2006) demonstrated that socio-economic factors of female criminality differ on the

basis of group, class, religion, income, rural, urban and education. Women in Pakistan are pushed to commit crimes due to socio-economic and cultural issues including a lack or low level of education, economic dependence, large family size and patriarchal system (Zafar, et al., 2013; Abbas & Manzoor, 2015; Das, 2013). In addition to these aspects, there is lack of information regarding total numbers of women prisoners and also major factors behind their criminality. The present study explored the socio-cultural causes of crime committed by imprisoned women in the different jails of the Punjab, province.

Literature Review:

Mili & Cherian (2015) conducted a study in India to explore the causes behind the female crime. Researchers found that crime is a behavioral, social, cultural, economic, and political problem that attracted women to commit it. The study further established that strained interpersonal relationship with the husband or other family members, husband extra marital affairs, deprivation, and denial of the basic need of life were major causes of frustration, which ultimately led to committing crimes by women.

Baloch (2011) conducted an explanatory study on women's prisons to explore dimensions of crime such as personal, socio-economic, and demographic. The study's results revealed that females were imprisoned for six types of crime i.e. drug trafficking, murder, kidnapping, robbery/theft, child trafficking, and extramarital relationships. Results further showed that low-income background, arranged marriages, marriage at early ages, exchange marriages and illiteracy were found major determinants of female criminality.

Khalid & Khan (2013) conducted a research study to examine the pathways to imprisonment for women in Pakistan. The study showed that the convicted women were belonged to poor and low-income families and had addiction problems with mental disorders, neglected in childhood, faced physical & sexual abuse. Researchers found the majority of the respondent committed crime firsttime the poverty the practice of dowry, spousal mistreatment, patriarchal family organization, and financial issues emerged as key reasons of the criminal behaviour.

Saeed, Rehman & Usmani (2018) conducted explanatory research to explore the relationship between socio-economic status and female

criminality, and to find out the pattern of crime among females. Researchers found that lust of money, inflation, unemployment, the role of media in the socialization process of women, unstable relation between husband & wife, extramarital affairs, interference, instigation of others, violence against women, harmful family environment and old customs & traditions were the major causes of increasing female criminality in the Pakistan.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To explore the socio-cultural determinants of female criminality
2. To discover economic factors behind the female criminality
3. To suggest corrective measures to control female criminality.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

For this study, researchers relied on purposive sampling technique. The participants included in this study were those who fulfilled the established criteria. List of prisons having convicted women were provided by the Punjab Prison, Government of Punjab includes (i) Central Jail, Lahore (ii) Central Jail, Gujranwala (iii) Central Jail Bahawalpur (iv) District Jail, Sheikhpura (v) District Jail, Sialkot (vi) Women Jail, Multan (vii) Central Jail, Sahiwal (viii) Central Jail, Rawalpindi (ix) District Jail, Attock (x) District Jail, Gujrat (xi) District Jail, Jhelum (xii) District Jail, Faisalabad (xiii) Central Jail. About 301 convicted women were imprisoned in the above-mentioned jails. The criteria include; (1) Pakistani national 18 or above 18 years convicted in any crime and (2) imprisoned in any of the above-mentioned prison of Punjab province of Pakistan. Married women mean a woman who had been married at least one time. A total of (N= 32) sample were drawn. Semi-structured interview guide was used to conduct the in-depth interviews with the convicted women by using possible relevant questions for the purpose of addressing socio-cultural and economic aspects of female criminality, background and demographic characteristics. According to jail manual, males were not allowed to visit the designated place of women prisoners. Therefore, two well-versed and experiences female enumerators were engaged to collect the data from the participants. In addition to increase the accuracy of the data collection, voice recorder was also used with permission of jail administration and the participants. The comfort

and neutral places within the premises of jail were selected to interview the participants.

Ethical Consideration:

The following ethical considerations have been observed:

Approval from the Punjab Prison Department, Government of Punjab was obtained to collect the data from the convicted women. Informed consent was also taken from every participant after explaining to them the nature and purpose of the study. Because of restriction of visit by males in the women barracks of jails, qualified and experienced female enumerators were engaged to collect the

data. Lastly, the confidentiality of respondents was ensured by considering the sensitivity of identity in every regard.

RESULTS:

The major focus of the current study was to explore socio-cultural and economic determinants of female criminality in Punjab, Pakistan. This study was actually descriptive in nature and a qualitative approach was used to collect the data by conducting in-depth interviews using an interview guide. Thematic analysis was carried out to produce trustworthy and insightful findings. Following themes emerged in the current study.

Table 1. Codes and Sub codes from In-depth Interviews

Domain	Final Codes and Sub codes
Nature of Criminality	<p>Frequent Crimes (FC):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ M-Murder □ DD-Drug Dealing □ T-Theft
Socio-Cultural Determinants	<p>Family Environment (FE):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ DV-Domestic Violence □ CE-Controlling Environment □ ED-Exclusion from Decisions
	<p>Husband's Behavior and Treatment (HBT)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ IPV-Intimate Partner Violence □ TDR-Trust Deficient Relationship □ BFB-Birth of Female gender
	<p>Trend of Marriage (TM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ FM-Forced Marriage □ EM-Early Marriage
	<p>Extramarital Affairs(EA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ USN-Unmet Sexual Need □ BP-Becoming Parents □ ML-Multiple Loving
	<p>Crime as Learned Behavior (CLB)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ PP-Peer Pressure □ FH-Family History
	<p>Revenge (R)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ PL-Pretended to Love □ D-Defamation
Economic Determinants	<p>Poverty (R)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ UBN-Unmet Basic Needs □ U-Unemployment □ I-Inflation
Elimination of Criminality	<p>Counteractive Measures (CM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ E-Education □ RFEM-Restriction on Forced & Early Marriages □ FS-Family Support

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (N= 32)

Demographic Variables	Total sample N (32)
Current Age	
18-29	5
33-39	24
40 and above	3
Age at the time of marriage	
>18	11
<18	21
Marital status	
Married	18
Unmarried	1
Divorced	3
Widow	10
Religion	
Muslim	31
Non-Muslim	1
Education Level	
Illiterate	22
Primary Education	4
Secondary Education	4
Higher	2
Education level of family members	
50 or more than 50 percent educated	5
50 or less than 50 percent uneducated	27
Type of Family	
Nuclear	6
Joint	26
Residential area	
Urban	12
Rural	20
Age difference between husband and wife	
<5 years	5
4-9 years	6
>10 years	20
Not Applicable	1
Occupation	
Housewife	16
Service/Job	1
Domestic servant	14
Business	1
Monthly household income	
Up to 5,000 rupees	03
Up to 10,000 rupees	07
Up to 15,000 rupees	16
>15,000 rupees	06
Children of respondent	
No child	5
1-2	5
3-4	8

>4	14
Language	
Punjabi	13
Saraiki	8
Urdu	6
Other	5

The above table showed that the 5 females out of 32 were doing crime at the age of 18-29, 24 were at age of 33-39 and 3 were in 40 and above. Age at the time of marriage <18, the questionnaire with frequency of 11 and 21 of >18 respectively. The majority of women (18) were married, only 1 female was unmarried, 03 female were divorced and 10 females were divorced. Similarly, 31 and 1 females were from Muslim religion and Non-Muslim respectively. The majority of the respondents were illiterate (22), 6 respondents had only primary education and 4 and 4 respondents were secondary and higher education respectively. The data shows that 50% or more than that family member of only 5 females were educated whereas the same ratio of 27 females were uneducated. The majority of the women (26) lived in joint family system while only 6 females belongs to the nuclear family system. The status of residential area status reflected that 12 respondents belonged to urban area and 20 women were from rural area. The age difference of 20 women were more than 10 years, 6 women were 4-9 years 5 women were <5 years. About 16 respondents were housewives, 14 were house maid and remaining 2 respondents belong to services/job and business respectively. The household monthly income of 3 women were up to 5000 rupees, 7 respondent were up to 10000 rupees, 16 women were up to 15000 rupees and 6 respondents monthly income were >15000 rupees. About 14 women had >4 child, 8 were 3-4, 5 were 1-2 and 5 respondents had no child. The mother language of 13 females was Punjabi, 8 were Saraiki, 6 were Urdu and 5 respondents were from other languages.

Theme-I: Nature of Crime

Data elements related to this theme were identified by questioning the respondents on nature of crime committed by the women. The convicted women demonstrated various crimes 'murder' identified as the most frequently applied code to researcher transcripts and emerged as a dominant theme. The convicted women expressed that they faced many serious problems in their life. Therefore, they

committed crime to get rid from such problems. One of the convicted women stated:

"I murdered my husband because he always demanded money and tortured me, if I refuse".

Another important subtheme emerged in the data set was drug trafficking. The convicted women expressed that they committed crime because of greed of handsome amount in return. One of the respondents demonstrated that:

"For the sake of handsome money, I was pushed into the crime of drug trafficking. Therefore, I was imprisoned for five years by the court".

Theme-II: Environment of Family

Data elements related to this theme was identified during the interviews in the response of question to convicted women with respect socio-cultural causes. The convicted women demonstrated various elements of female criminality in relation to the environment of family. But domestic violence was identified most frequently applied descriptive code to researcher transcripts and emerged as a dominant theme. The convicted women expressed that harmful environment of family was a major determinant of their criminality. The convicted women expressed that they faced domestic violence from their mother-in-law, sister-in-law, brother-in-law, and father-in-law. They explained that they tried to tolerate it at the maximum level. But they had lost their temperament and committed crime. One of the convicted women stated:

"My mother-in-law and sister-in-law did nothing but constantly humiliated me all the time. One day, they started to quell with men. During a fight, I picked up a knife from the kitchen and attacked my sister-in-law. As a result, she was seriously injured and eventually lost her life. I was arrested by the police for her murder and was sentenced to life imprisonment by the court".

In the transcript, controlling environment emerged as another important subtheme. Convicted women expressed that the involvement of other family members in the personal affairs of husband and wife

had disturbed the whole environment of the family. Another convicted woman revealed:

"My mother-in-law always interfered in our personal affairs. I tolerated a lot but one day, my patience paid off and I killed my mother-in-law".

Another important subtheme identified in the data set was exclusion from the decision-making process at home. The respondents demonstrated that they were kept away from every decision-making process of household matters which created disorder in the family environment. One of the respondents narrated:

"I murdered my husband because he decided to marry my daughter to his nephew without taking opinion from me."

Theme-III: Husband's behavior and Treatment

Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) emerged frequently dominated applied codes in the dataset. The respondents demonstrated that harsh and violent behavior of husband was responsible for their crime. One of these respondents said:

"I murdered my husband because of his frequent violence every time. He had abused and tortured me daily. He had not given household expenses and on the other hand he had demanded money from me to buy alcohol and other types of intoxication."

Convicted women explained that trust deficient relationship between husband and wife was major cause of criminality. One of the respondents told:

"My husband had always been suspicious about me. Therefore, his attitude was not normal with me. Ultimately, I had been fed up with such behavior and I killed my husband".

The convicted women demonstrated that their husbands had done violence against them because of birth of female gender. They expressed that their husbands had the views that women are responsible for the birth of female babies. One of the respondents narrated:

*"I faced physical violence from my husband every time. Because I had two daughters. He was of the view that woman is responsible for this. Ultimately, it was beyond my patience and therefore, I murdered my **husband**".*

Theme-IV: Trends of Marriage:

During the interviews with convicted women, it is found that the majority of women were not happy with their marriages. The respondents claimed that they were married forcefully or without their consent. They apprised that they committed

serious crime to get rid from such types of mismatched marriages. One of the respondents told:

"I murdered seventeen family members to get rid of my marriage. My father forcefully married me with my cousin whereas I was in love with a neighbor boy".

Beside the above, marriage at early age proved one of the major causes of female criminality. The majority of the respondents stated that they were married at their early ages and they were not ready to handle household responsibilities.

"I was married at early age due to which I was unable to perform household responsibilities. This created clashes between me and my in-laws. Resultantly, the disputes increased which led to commit crime against my mother in law. I murdered my mother in law during fight".

Theme-V: Extramarital Affairs

The convicted women demonstrated that extramarital affairs of husband and wife were emerged major cause of female criminality. They further explained that unmet sexual needs and desire of becoming parents are major reasons behind extramarital affairs. The respondents demonstrated that they committed a crime to avoid from stigmatization in the society. Furthermore, some of the respondents stated that they murdered their husband because of their extramarital affairs with other women. One of the respondent narrated:

"I murdered my husband because he had been known about my extramarital affairs with a neighbor. I developed relations with a neighbour because my husband could not fulfill my sexual need".

'Becoming a mother' was emerged another subtheme in the data set. The respondents explained that they developed extramarital affairs to become mother because their husbands were not able to become father. One of the respondent demonstrated:

"My husband was not able to fulfil my sexual desire for becoming mother. Therefore, I developed extra marital relationship with my cousin. My husband came to know about this relationship and threaten to kill me and my cousin. Before, he turned his threat into action, I killed him".

Another subtheme emerged in the data set was 'multiple loving'. The respondents demonstrated that their husbands had passionate of developing extramarital affairs with other women. Therefore, they murdered their husbands. One of the respondent said:

“When I came to know about the extramarital affairs of my husband with other woman. I could not tolerate this and killed my husband”.

Theme-VI: Crime as learned behavior

Supporting role of peer group in learning and adopting criminal behavior from family member was emerged as contributing factors in female criminality. The convicted women demonstrated that they committed crime on invitation of their friends and family members. One of the respondent said:

“One of my best friend was drug trafficker. She had a huge amount every time. I was highly influenced to see her living standard. I joined her company on her invitation and started business of drug dealing”.

Family history was emerged another important subtheme which reflected that family history was one of the major determinant of female criminality. One of the convicted women told:

“I was born in a poor family. My mother along with her friends used to rob and steal things like clothes and grocery items to fulfil household needs. After my marriage, I also started to steal things with my mother”.

Theme-VII: Revenge

The element of revenge triggered females to commit crime. The convicted women demonstrated two elements of revenge in which ‘pretended to love’ identified most frequent subtheme. The respondents narrated that they committed crime to take revenge. One of the respondent stated:

“I killed my first cousin because he refused to marry me although we were in love with each other. He cheated on me and decided to marry with another girl. Therefore, I murdered him”.

Defamation identified another important sub theme. The convicted women demonstrated that they committed crime due to defamation. One of the respondent explained:

“I killed the husband of my sister-in-law because he always complaint my husband against me”.

Theme-VIII: Poverty

Besides the socio-cultural factors, economic factors economic emerged significant factors behind the female criminality. Various sub-themes were identified under the major theme poverty. However, ‘unmet basic needs’ explored most frequent applied code. The convicted women illustrated that they committed crime due to

poverty. They explained that they had preferred crime to fulfil the basic needs of their children. One of the respondent said:

“My husband has died 3 years ago. After his death, I had no mean of earning. Therefore, I was very upset and start stealing to fulfil household. One day, the shopkeeper caught me red handed and handed over to police in the case of robbery instead of stealing”.

Another important subtheme identified in the data set was ‘unemployment’. Many respondents narrated that they had shifted to the urban area for the sake of employment. However, they could not successful in getting employment and ultimately they indulged in the criminal activities for their source of income. One of the respondents demonstrated:

“I had been shifted in the city to search livelihood opportunities but failed. Though, my household expenses had been increased due to shifting in the city and earning of my husband was insufficient. Ultimately, I have to choose the path of crime to fulfil my household expense”.

Additionally, inflation was explored another major sub-theme in the data set. Most of the women described that inflation is one of the major cause of female criminality. They explained that their income was not sufficient to meet expense of household because of high inflation. They have to select the path of crime to fulfil their household needs. One of the respondent said:

“My husband was laborer and his income was not sufficient to meet daily expense of household. I had been started work as domestic servant but we could not fulfil household needs. Therefore, I had been involved in the drug dealing”.

Theme-IX: Corrective Measures

In the response of question to the respondents regarding corrective measures, the majority of the convicted women demonstrated various sub codes includes education, employment opportunities, restriction on forced & early marriages and family support. They described that the above mentioned elements may overcome female criminality. One of the respondent stated:

“I understand that, education may reduce female criminality so government should make strong education system within jail and outside the jail for both male and female”.

Another respondent narrated:

“Awareness to men and women regarding their rights and obligations may reduce female criminality”.

The convicted women demonstrated that the government should take measures to fulfil the gaps in the criminal justice system so that the timely decision may be taken. One of the respondent narrated:

"The government may identify issues in criminal justice system and take measures for fulfilling the gaps".

Another respondent demonstrated:

"The government should properly execute the laws to end forced and child marriages to reduce women criminality".

The majority of the respondents claimed that the supportive behavior of the family at every sphere of life may play key role in eliminating female criminality. One of the respondents said:

"If my family had supported me, I would not have been punished, rather conciliation would have been done".

Discussion:

The core purpose of this research was to explore the socio-cultural determinants of female criminality in Punjab. It is a striking fact that rate of female criminality is increasing day by day. It was highly essential to dig out the grounded and embedded social and cultural factors to deter the deviant behavior of females in Punjab. The study reflected that women are imprisoned for different nature of crimes. However, murder and drug trafficking emerged as prominent crimes committed by women. The above findings also endorsed by the many previous studies. The previous studies demonstrated that murder and drug trafficking are popular crimes committed by women ([Avais & Wassan, 2017](#); [Warraich & Farooq, 2015](#); [Baloch, 2011](#); [Naqvi, Ibrar, & Haider, 2015](#)).

Thematic analysis reflected that the unpleasant environment within the family triggered the violence against women. The same results were found by ([Hagan & Daigle, 2018](#); [Saeed, Rehman, & Usmani, 2018](#)). Sometimes, women react in the form of deviant behavior and committed heinous offenses consequently. Mostly, the causes of offenses were grounded within the family setting ([Warraich & Farooq, 2015](#); [Semise, Makatu, & Nkoana, 2015](#); [Aslam, Raza, & Ijaz, 2015](#); [Avais & Waseem, 2017](#)).

Theme related to husband's harsh and violent behavior, the results demonstrated that such behavior played significant role in committing crime by women which is common in our society. These results are similar to the results extracted in the previous studies which stated that violent behavior of husbands pushed women to commit a

crime against them ([Bhandari, 2018](#); [Sahin, 2015](#); [Khan, Aeron, & Townsend, 2006](#); [Baloch, 2011](#); [Ali & Ganvino, 2007](#); [Townhead, 2006](#)). Furthermore, the study reflected that the forced marriages or the marriages without the consent of females were explored as key factors in adopting criminal behavior by females which is also endorsed by the previous studies. The practice of forced marriage ([Islam, Farooq, & Mahmood, 2019](#); [Hadi, 2017](#)), early marriage ([Jensen & Thornton, 2003](#); [Islam, Amjad, & Yaseen, 2021](#)) and mismatched marriage ([Avais & Wassan, 2017](#)) emerged as major socio-cultural determinants of female criminality in the society.

Besides the above, extramarital affairs of husband and wife were observed as significant determinants of female criminality in the thematic analysis. Firstly, women had killed their family members' particularly their husbands to avoid stigma or fear of any action against them because their husbands had known about their illicit relationship. Secondly, women killed their husbands when they had known about extra-marital affairs of their husbands with other women. They could not tolerate defame of their husband and killed them. The above results are endorsed by ([Islam, Farooq, & Mahmood, 2019](#); [Warraich & Farooq, 2015](#); [Walayat, Hasan, & Ajmal, 2013](#); [Tariq & Anila, 1993](#)).

Moreover, the results of the study described that crime is learned behavior which was learnt from the peer group by the convicted women. The convicted women confirmed that they committed crime on the invitation of their friends. The above findings are related to the results of the previous studies conducted by ([Islam, Farooq, & Mahmood, 2019](#); [Azad, Hau & Karlsson, 2018](#); [Musa & Ahmed, 2015](#); [Aslam, Raza, & Ijaz, 2015](#); [Wike, Miller, Winn, & Taylor, 2013](#)). Apart from the peer pressure, the convicted women were blaming and cursing their family members for indulging them in the world of crime. They explained that someone of their family members i.e. parents, brothers, sisters or husbands were involved in the criminal activities. These findings are related to the outcomes of the studies conducted by ([Eriksson et al., 2016](#); [Khalid & Khan, 2013](#); [Fergusson, Campbell, & Horwood, 2004](#)). The thematic analysis further found that the element of revenge was also proved driving force for the female criminality. Most of the respondents committed crime just to take revenge which is endorsed by

(Islam, Farooq, & Mahmood, 2019; Warraich & Farooq, 2015; Dogar et al., 2010; Khalid & Khan, 2009).

Lastly, economic factors such as poverty discovered major determinant of female criminality. The respondents demonstrated their views that unmet basic needs, unemployment and inflation were major contributing factors behind the poverty. The previous studies endorsed that poverty/unemployment is one of the major cause of female criminality (Saeed, Rehman, & Usmani, 2018; Khalid & Khan, 2013; Alfred & Chlup, 2009).

Conclusion:

Male and female are the essential building blocks of the human society. For the healthy and progressive society, it is highly necessary that both, male and female play proactive and productive role. The deviant behavior or criminal act of male or female is a harmful for the socio-cultural fabric of the society. The present research is also concerted efforts to explore the socio-cultural determinants of female criminality in Punjab, Pakistan.

It is concluded that socio-cultural factors includes harmful environment of family, Intimate Partner Violence(IPV), grotesque practice of forced and early marriages, peer influence, extra-marital affairs, family history, inheritance property rights and preference to taking revenge were major socio-cultural factors behind the female criminality. Beside the socio-cultural factors, economic factors such as poverty and unemployment found major factors behind the female criminality. Hence it is proved that female criminality is entrenched in the society, therefore, it is the need of hour to deter the socio-cultural factors which are the responsible for the female criminality.

Recommendations:

The convicted women proposed their recommendations to overcome the female criminality in the Punjab. The recommendations includes education, awareness raising campaign about rights and obligation of male and female, family support, and strict policies regarding elimination of domestic violence, forced marriage and early marriage. The researchers further recommended that female criminality could be reduced and conviction rate can be minimized by playing of positive & collective role of the family of respondents, relatives, neighbors, political

representatives, religious leaders, police, lawyers, court, mass media and the civil society.

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